

ADVANCING INCLUSION THROUGH SPORTS: STUDIES AND SUCCESS STORIES

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Abstract:

Motor and sports activity is relevant from the earliest years of life and can improve the quality of life. This paper analyses the value of play as a start to sporting activity. Specifically, in a process of inclusion, movement encourages people with disabilities to acquire self-awareness through the perception of their bodies. In this framework, the culture of encounter, confrontation and inclusion are the key elements that form the educational method of Scholas Occurrentes. Scholas' mission is to transform the world into an inclusive society, through better education and integration of communities, focusing on those with fewer resources, involving all social partners, from schools to educational networks around the world, starting from educational, sports and artistic proposals. In this sense, sport is seen as a vehicle to increase self-esteem and self-confidence, to promote physical, psychological and social well-being with a view to improving the quality of life understood as the subjective perception that each individual has of his or her position, in the cultural and value context in which he or she fits in, also and above all in relation to his or her goals, expectations and concerns.

Keywords: *Play-Sport; Inclusion; Didactics of Movement.*

Introduction

Motor activity is fundamental for the correct development of the individual since, thanks to the discovery and exploration of one's own body, the environment, movement and playful activity, one has the opportunity to learn numerous skills in the various developmental areas, getting to know oneself and others better, one's own potential and limits, and the social and emotional rules that guide interpersonal relationships. Through sport it is possible to improve the balance between body and mind, aiming at maintaining and developing skills and qualities. Sport, therefore, makes it possible to stimulate and strengthen one's resources, which, in the long term, can become instruments of great strength and adaptation, capable of consolidating one's self-efficacy (Bidzan-Bluma, & Lipowska, 2018). Education through movement and sport can offer a tangible opportunity to acquire early on the foundational assumptions of sharing, built by people through mutual

interactions, and used as a daily resource to interpret and give meaning to social and cultural life. In the educational-motor field, it is indispensable to look at the didactics of movement as a system of symbols and tools that help the individual to amplify his or her cognitive capacities through bodily-kinesthetics'

experience. From this perspective, the school can take on the task of teaching the construction of knowledge through the acquisition of alternative languages for reading reality, including the non-verbal language of a motor character. Precisely from this perspective, motor activities in school can represent a valid transversal methodological support for the achievement of objectives and goals in an interdisciplinary key (Dapp, & Roebers, 2019). The didactics of movement, therefore, is not only understood as the development of motor skills and abilities, but requires the transition from mere education of the body to possible education through the body and in this sense is not only focused on disciplinary knowledge, but above all on the procedures that allow the motor area to produce potentially transferable knowledge and skills (Bruner, 1998). The transferability of disciplinary content through the motor-work experience opens up access to multiple knowledge, capable of simultaneously anchoring itself to different cognitive and sensory-perceptive channels. The body becomes an interacting subject for problem solving, for the reworking of complementary or alternative strategies of knowledge, a true didactic support engine. By identifying the body and movement as intelligent dimensions of the individual, motor activities are recognised as having considerable educational and training value due to the potential they express in the ability to transfer knowledge and knowledge through the body in an original manner (Du et al., 2012). In the didactics of movement, a didactics of the body, with the body and for the body, the bodily-kinesthetics' dimension, in the plurality of intellectual forms, translates in the didactic sphere into a possible elaboration of teaching methodologies that are not only usable in the motor field, but highly significant on the cognitive, emotional, expressive and relational levels that allow the person to act with respect to problematic situations, the characteristics of which require different and specific approaches, methods and choices and, for each context, engage personal systems of decoding and subsequent codification.

1. The Game: Primary Motivation for Movement

Play, relegated by a widespread and erroneous belief among purely childish activities, is instead a fundamental need common to all individuals of both sexes, whatever their age or culture. In the adult individual, the willingness to play is not diminished, as is commonly believed (Di Battista, & Vivaldo, 2015). Sport is a game, and moreover an institutionalised game, in which ritualised, culturally organised, socially finalised playful expressions can be found, fuelled by deep affective experiences and explicit cognitive needs (Lu, Nagappan, & Lu, 2014). Play presents itself as an activity with complex characteristics, increasingly symbolically organised as one moves towards adulthood. The characteristics of play are given by:

- Elements of uncertainty that can be partially controlled, in which emotion can leverage the unpredictability of the situation and the possibility of experiencing the situation itself in terms of pleasant anxiety and measured Risk;
- A simple norm accepted by all, temporally and spatially established, which can be invented, abandoned, reconstructed, without resulting in established roles or irrevocable penalties;
- A condition in which the individual can construct in symbolic (cultural and emotional) terms a fictional reality capable of optimising the realisation of subjective needs.
- The child's fantasy play, with open eyes or in the complete possibility of using reality for hallucinatory projections, is the classic and original expression of all forms of play. It is evident how these characteristics of play can be traced in many sporting situations. There are games with predominantly motor, symbolic, normative and creative content, and therefore games that are more or

less suitable for absorbing and expressing biopsychic rather than socio-emotional needs or vice versa. The pleasure a child can derive from a sports activity (preparatory play gymnastics sessions) is to be linked to a play situation, in which movement (biopsychic) and relationship (psychosocial) needs are satisfied (Sheikh, Bay, Ghorbani, & Esfahani Nia, 2022). If the sports animator is aware of this, he or she must take care to plan the activity, on the one hand by widely diversifying the game exercises so that they are always new and stimulating, and on the other by organising the same exercises within a satisfying relational moment. The older the children, the greater the interest the animator must place on the group situation; in this way a motivational element such as the need for movement can be finalised and maintained within a gratifying and learning social situation. Play is also a biological activity aimed at and used by the individual to restore the neuro-dynamic balance by means of a motor discharge. This motivation is considered important, even if today it has been downgraded, because the first complex motor learning, the initial rudiments of play and the motivating pleasure of play itself are linked to it (Martins et al., 2020). More recent studies agree that the organism tends not only to reduce internal impulses or achieve a state of calm, but also to actively seek new stimuli. The experiment is well known in this regard, according to which placing subjects in a situation of sensory deprivation (controlled elimination of any kind of perceptual-motor stimulus) results in the accentuation of movement fantasies and hunger for sensory stimuli, to the point of causing compensatory hallucinations. There are therefore good reasons for integrating the theory of homeostatic mechanisms (internal balance) with that of nerve activation, recognising that part of the motivation for movement and play derives from the individual's need to maintain an optimal level of nerve activation (Tomporowski, & Pesce, 2020). In developmental individuals, this level is always in precarious equilibrium. An increase, or decrease, in this optimal condition causes the individual to immediately seek stimuli to make the level of nervous activation constant again. Play as a multiform, flexible activity, adjustable at will, lends itself effectively to this purpose. Every culture has elaborated an infinity of playful moments, more or less organised and institutional, to allow the expression of this primary need. A bored child, who receives less stimulation, is inclined to seek out new competitive play situations, which are somehow offered to him standardised in the form of entertainment, games, and sports, by society or even by the peer group. It happens that certain cultural devices to control the "hunger" for stimuli and the optimal level of nervous activation can compete with each other (Margiotta, 2016). A typical example is that of today's child who, captured by the strong perceptive sensory stimulation of the television message or, above all, the media message of the Net, tends to lose exploratory orientation, motor initiative and sensory curiosity.

2. Play and Motivation

Cognitive motivation can be defined as the active search for the conditions that enable the individual to understand, control and modify life situations with respect to the environment and the problem-solving that this process entails. The psychomotor experience present in games and conversely in sport satisfies the individual's cognitive motivations; these are expressed in conducts ranging from the pure exploration of the environment to imaginative activity of the ideomotor type, i.e. the real or imaginary manipulation of objects and mastering the body, situations and physical space (Epstein, 1989). This exploratory need involves the sensory-perceptive and intellectual functions that find their first verification and development in psychomotor experience. The first sensemotor experiences are the basis for all subsequent stages of learning and intelligence development. From birth, children develop their psychic faculties by passing through various stages, which are closely interconnected. From an initial

phase of pure, global, subcortical motility, typical of the first weeks of life, the child passes in the first months of life to a capacity to receive sensory stimulation, and through this, to the regulation of motor acts. Towards the middle of the first year, urged on by elementary cognitive motivations, he begins to move towards objects, to manipulate them, to play embryonic exercise games. Subsequently, the movement itself stimulates in the child the enrichment of sensory experiences, the control of reality and the realisation of further reinforcements tending increasingly towards this process of active adaptation to the environment. The conquest of a sense-motor mastery of reality has as its starting point the continuous interaction between the body as an immediate science of oneself and the environment as a projection of one's cognitive intentionality (Errisuriz, Golaszewski, Born, & Bartholomew, 2018). In each sporting activity, there is an abundance of perceptual and memory, visual, auditory and tactile input, and in particular kinaesthetic input relating to the perception of one's own body in movement, so as to engage the individual in a broad and detailed manner in internal and external perception. The inner drive that stimulates the child's interest in things, new situations and motor experimentation is basically the same as that which appears in certain games and, in a sometimes exemplary or veiled manner, in many sporting disciplines. The game, therefore, allows one to discover new possibilities, to experience the attraction of risk, to give oneself over to illusion, to express oneself, to achieve a new and original result. In this sense, sport makes the cognitive need its own through the continual invention of disciplines, techniques, changes, opportunities, in which the creative element appears, either as a dominant need (as, for example, in basketball or mountaineering or spearfishing), or as a less perceptible secondary need (as, for example, in rowing or cross-country racing, where the element of creative experimentation occurs more on the tactical level and as an activity of inner and psychophysical control). The sports instructor and entertainer should know that the child's play and physical activity are subject to the need for imagination and fantasy (Margiotta, 2009). Playful expression, especially if left free, is always rich in individual creative potential, as the child must invent, through gestures and the use of new motor schemes, behaviours capable of establishing a continuous modification of action in relation to the surrounding world. This is why certain sports, in which the element of boredom and the automatic repetitiveness of the gesture is particularly present while the creative-cognitive element is absent, are so frequently abandoned by adolescents. The boy who tries to bounce a stone off the water or who attempts to jump over a ditch, is merely confronting precise psycho-motor problems in which he is strongly engaged on a cognitive level. In this perspective, sport, when imbued with play situations, is by no means a series of useless motor expressions, but rather an activity of reflection, choice, and reinvention. In particular, during pre-adolescence, sporting practice must be organised, proposed and enriched with game elements of a cognitive nature, otherwise it runs the risk of rapidly saturating the child's interest and decreasing motivation just as quickly. Pre-adolescents' games are oriented towards psychomotor activities in which exploratory and ideational commitment is particularly present and felt (Colella, 2016). In them, there is extensive reference to intellectual activities (memory, evaluation, expressiveness), ideational content (figurative, symbolic, behavioral) and mental operations (union, relation, transformation). In general, many sporting activities contain, albeit not explicitly, all these cognitive factors: think, for example, of a simple football match, artistic gymnastics, etc. There are sports whose game content is more or less saturated with cognitive factors that are suitable for all those young people, for whom the playful element of sporting practice serves to achieve a predominantly cognitive activity; whereas in other subjects the motivating playful element may be more of an exquisitely affective nature, characterized by emotional dynamisms. Think, for example, of those sporting activities in which

the element of play is given by the alternation of emotions, unexpected events, and calculated risks (Cecilian, 2015). Children's raids in the countryside, at the seaside, in city neighbourhoods; games among ancient ruins and simulated battles are the equivalent of alpine hiking, football matches, caving sports or underwater fishing. In childhood, it happens that the choice or abandonment of a particular game seems to obey different purposes: especially when the playful activity symbolically reconstructs on the outside the needs and experiences corresponding to the inner reality. Play, contrary to common opinion, is not an activity relegated to childhood and incapable of surviving into maturity. Adults, in order to tolerate the presence of play in their reality, have had to relegate it to the ritualized functions of leisure time and invent theories to prove its usefulness to the child. Sporting practice that accommodates emotional drives more properly linked to desire means that play can persist in a serious activity while concealing its profound affective implications. In relation to the psychodynamic mechanisms that induce the young person to find moments of profound affective gratification in the playful situation, it is necessary to reflect on the fact that they also persist in sport, albeit amalgamated with agonism and hidden by the rational and realistic sense of sporting activity. Let us take the example of a 15-year-old young man, who has been passionately practicing basketball for a short time. Most probably this young man, if interviewed, would not be able to say what motivates him to play this sport and what in particular amuses him (Castelli, Hillman, Buck, & Erwin, 2007). A large part of the motivations remain obscure to the subject himself, linked as they are to the deepest affective dynamisms which, although they exercise an important role in guiding behaviour, remain foreign to his consciousness. For this youngster, the game of basketball has, among other things, a reassuring function, as it allows him to release considerable emotional charges through fantasy and motor activity. These fantasies are primarily representative of libidinal and aggressive drives. Sport enables him to symbolically dramatize past interpersonal situations, to resolve tensions with parental figures, to find and overcome feelings of dependence, insecurity, ego-affirmation, and to recognize himself as an individual with a transformed corporeity compared to childhood (Babic et al., 2014). Therefore, sport must allow, through appropriate regulatory mediations, the free expression of aggression, since its denial or removal can cause neurotic or self-destructive disturbances. Sport is thus found to be one of the few human activities in which the aggressive drive can be completely released and can manifest itself in a no repressed and deformed manner. Sport would therefore be motivated, in personal and collective terms, by the need to create institutional situations suitable for releasing deep-seated anxieties, such as the persecutory and depressive ones. The athlete manifests the aggressive core of agonism against the following factors: Nature, understood as the difficulties inherent in the sporting specialty (e.g. a mountain to climb, a weight to lift, an implement to juggle, etc.) and overcoming the difficulties allows the athlete his own affirmation; Self, through hard sacrifices, made up of intense training and directed towards a rigorous goal, in which the competitive element is established between the real and ideal self. The adversary, as a real person or phantasmal image, considered more as a means than as an objective, an element to be emulated and overcome rather than annihilated. Sport, like any human activity, can be fuelled by psychological needs that draw their stimuli from inner conflicts, forms of emotional distress, abnormal character traits, and social maladjustment. The choice to practice a certain sporting discipline can serve the individual as a means of compensating, resolving, expressing certain neurotic valences of his or her personality (Almond, 2013). It should be borne in mind that, alongside motivational vectors, drives of neurotic origin may appear in the athlete, with a more or less relevant role, many times not ascribable

to a particularly disturbed personality framework, which, fitting perfectly into the type of performance and emotional involvement required, manage to find their own adaptation in the sporting situation.

3. Inclusive Game-Sport Didactics

Playful and competitive practice functions either as a defensive mechanism or as a liberating situation. It is for this reason that intuitively it seems that those with a particular inner discomfort are able to orient themselves towards the sporting discipline most congenial to them. Among the most common reasons, in which sport functions as a compensatory situation, are the following:

- Feelings of inferiority. Certain deficits of a physical, psychic or even social nature, experienced with an abnormal reactivity, may lead the young person to engage in activities, such as sport, capable of disproving or compensating for these real or presumed inferiorities. In addition, the shy, the insecure, the anxious, the hypercritical towards oneself may feel motivated to sport precisely by the desire to continually verify, through an objective test bench, one's abilities and possibilities.
- Desire for power. It may occur that the bearer of a latent feeling of inferiority tries, reactively, to deny it in its opposite (superiority) through situations that allow him the greatest affirmation of the self. Sport in this case becomes the ideal stage on which the athlete, thus motivated, tries to fulfil this desire, with all the risks and psychic frustrations that this attempt entails (e.g. the alternation of victory-loss).
- The sociopathic model of aggressive masculinity. It is based on the desire to conform as closely as possible to the models of courage, grit, aggressiveness and bravura put forward as the exaggerated masculine ideal.

We can define play as any individual or collective activity carried out for the pleasure its very practice brings, without any purpose other than pure enjoyment. For the young of many animals, play plays a fundamental role in the development of physical and mental abilities. By playing, the young animal learns all it needs about itself and its environment, and thus acquires behaviour that in the future will be fundamental for the practical and relational life of its species. For the child, who has to prepare for much more complex relational behaviour, play is even more important (Bardid, De Meester, Tallir, Cardon, Lenoir, & Haerens, 2016). Through play, he begins to understand how objects can be used, becomes aware of the existence of rules of behaviour that must be respected, learns to persevere and have confidence in his abilities, and at the same time gives vent to his imagination and creativity. Play plays a fundamental role not only in childhood, but also in adult life, and over the years takes on an endless array of different values and meanings. Suffice it to say that since antiquity, play has been used in religious celebrations in honour of deities, as a form of training in the military art, as a moment of conviviality, and later acquired a particular social and civic value. However, play is often understood as a synonym for fun, leisure, superficiality as an end in itself, as a moment of disengagement, so that it is confused with something of little significance, something superfluous because it is not directly useful for achieving an objective. In reality, it constitutes for man a moment of maximum commitment, in which an effort is made to produce the best performance. Through play, we practise getting to know new situations, testing our skills, exploiting previous experiences, understanding the strategies of others in order to cope with them better, improving our motor imagination. So the game helps us get to know each other better, improve our personality and develop our intelligence. During play we are constantly forced to make decisions, and the quicker and more effective they prove to be, the higher the quality of the game (Chaddock, Pontifex, Hillman, & Kramer, 2011). Play, especially for adults, turns into an

individual or collective activity of comparison, into a competition to affirm certain cultural roots, overcome the difficulties of natural environments and demonstrate acquired skills. With the awareness that it is possible to learn through play, it is fundamental, however, that the comparison is experienced as a moment of growth, an opportunity for learning and improvement, and not instead as a chance to prove oneself better than others, with denigrating intentions. There are many ways in which games can be expressed: there are word games, charades, poetic games, games that were played in the Middle Ages such as tournaments, jousts, equestrian stakes; board games with cards, pawns, dice, etc.; games of skill and prestidigitation; puzzle and mathematical games; games that are expressed with physical gestures, called games of movement; sports games. Play as entertainment and pastime for children and adults was for a long time the preserve of the wealthy classes. In the middle Ages, for example, only the nobility took part in jousts, tournaments and equestrian stakes, in which knights displayed their skills of courage, dexterity and precision. Sport should be fun, play, confrontation for the pleasure of competing with others in a motor activity and not to bully or humiliate opponents in a spirit of overpowering or violence. Therefore, if the true spirit of sport can be kept alive, it can certainly become one of the fundamental objectives of motor sciences, especially with a view to the acquisition and consolidation of healthy lifestyle habits. In this sense, it should be emphasized that sporting activity, as a game, stimulates not only the physical but also the mental and even emotional components of the individual. Exercising personal freedom while respecting that of others, dealing with successes and defeats with balance, reacting promptly to sudden changes in situations, making use of the imagination and creativity, are all manifestations of a complete personality, to which recreational sporting activity can undoubtedly give a considerable boost (Dowling, & Washington, 2021). Sport is a game, and moreover an institutionalized game, in which ritualized, culturally organized, socially finalized playful expressions can be found, fuelled by deep affective experiences and explicit cognitive needs. Play presents itself as an activity with complex characteristics, increasingly symbolically organized as one moves towards adulthood. The characteristics of play are given by:

- Elements of uncertainty that can be partially controlled, in which emotion can leverage the unpredictability of the situation and the possibility of experiencing the situation itself in terms of pleasant anxiety and measured risk;
- A simple norm accepted by all, temporally and spatially established, which can be invented, abandoned, reconstructed, without resulting in established roles or irrevocable penalties;
- A condition in which the individual can construct in symbolic (cultural and emotional) terms a fictitious reality capable of optimizing the realization of subjective needs. It is evident how these game characters can be traced in many sporting situations. Suffice it to think, for example, of a teenager skiing alone down a mountain slope, off-piste, here the element of unpredictability and pleasurable anxiety is evident, just as the transgressed element of off-piste skiing, together with the possibility of experimenting a new situation in cognitive and normative terms, offers the possibility for the teenager to imagine himself as capable and powerful as an established champion. In relation to an educational intervention that aims to promote the psychomotricity of pupils with disabilities, it is necessary to consider the characteristics of the pupils and to bear in mind the difference between the different limitations that can be of a psychic, physical and sensorial nature. Disability is a condition linked to a physical or mental impairment, handicap is the consequence of disability on a social level. Handicap is the mirror of a society that lacks active solidarity, which allows itself to be transformed by accepting and adapting to the needs of those who are different. As handicap is the mirror of a society that is unwilling

to accept disadvantaged individuals, education has a fundamental task at every age, which is to transmit the value of inclusion. Inclusion understood as an educational and human value, is not only linked to the school context, it does not only concern a teacher, but fostering inclusion and thus psycho-social well-being, is everyone's responsibility and concerns every context (Belgianni, 2017). Psychomotricity is an activity that promotes the child's motor and cognitive maturation through movement. Movement has an effect on different areas of the person: on the intellectual area, favoring the development of perceptive processes, problem-solving skills; on the social area, favoring the ability to collaborate, to interact with the group, respect for rules; on the affective area, favoring security and trust and the control of emotionality and impulsiveness. What has been said reinforces the need for awareness as to what consequences each action may have, the intervention cannot be extemporaneous, but must be programmed, based on certain and real knowledge. The educator must take care to programme the activity, diversifying it and adapting it to the pupil's needs. Well, psychomotricity refers to everything that is manifested through the body, it considers the subject in its entirety deducible from the integration of the terms "psyche" and "motility", and it considers cognitive, motor, relational and affective aspects. Linked to psychomotricity is play, everything passes through play as a natural experience. Bruner defines play as "the most serious activity of childhood", play is a fundamental activity for the child, and it encourages the development, through the body, of motor, cognitive and social skills.

Operationally, we have different types of play:

- Sense-motor games. The child explores the world with his or her body, which becomes the channel through which the child gets to know, is a means of dialoguing with reality;
- Imitation games. Children play by imitating the world of adults;
- Regulated play. It is linked to moral education, it has internal rules, fundamental to understanding the importance of rules;
- Group games. Irrespective of the game itself, what prevails at these times, from the point of view of the child's growth, is the presence of the group, which encourages socialisation and cooperation;
- Symbolic games. A symbol takes on a meaning that will be expressed in the action. The action takes on the full value of the symbolic game, as it enables the child to mediate between the self and reality;
- Sports initiation games. These are activities with defined rules that constitute an initiation into sport. Play allows motor literacy, it is the starting point for developing skills, motor patterns and motor abilities.

4. The Culture of Encounter and the Scholas Occurrentes Educational Project

The Scholas Occurrentes Educational Project, as an International Educational Movement created by Pope Francis, carries out educational experiences with young people of different faiths and cultures on the five continents, in response to the deep thirst for meaning that is present in these times. Its goal is to promote the culture of encounter for peace through education. Promoting this culture means first and foremost inclusion: throughout its years of activity, Scholas has brought together young people from public and private schools, from different social, cultural and religious backgrounds. At the same time, it has pursued a paradigmatic change on how the educational process is conceived and constructed, understanding education not as "a role" to be delegated exclusively to schools and teachers, but as a much more articulated and participatory path, which must therefore involve families, institutions, organizations and all members of the community. What has caused the most concern, prompting Scholas to think very quickly about an appropriate pedagogical approach, is the socio-emotional health

of young people and belonging to the school community. School not only as a place of instruction but also as an opportunity for authentic relationships, the one that brings to the surface the questions of the heart and strives to find new paths to follow. This is the proposal of the Scholas Citizenship project promoted by the Pontifical Scholas Occurrentes Foundation in collaboration with the Ministry of Education. The culture of encounter, confrontation and inclusion are the key elements that form the educational method of Scholas Occurrentes. Scholas' mission is to transform the world into an inclusive society, through better education and integration of communities, focusing on those with fewer resources, involving all social partners, from schools to educational networks around the world, starting from educational, sports and artistic proposals. In this sense, sport is seen as a vehicle to increase self-esteem and self-confidence, to promote physical, psychological and social well-being with a view to improving the quality of life understood as the subjective perception that each individual has of his or her position, in the cultural and value context in which he or she fits in, also and above all in relation to his or her goals, expectations and concerns.

Between the walls of the classrooms are reproduced the same fractures that suffocate today's society. This is why Pope Francesco has proposed tearing down the walls and opening the doors. The result is an international network of schools from five continents. A "classroom-world" where young people of all cultures and religions exchange experiences, confront each other, learn to live together. The Scholas are laboratories of the culture of encounter. Their goal is to change the world through inclusive education, sports, art.

Conclusions

Play and sport are fundamental to education and psychophysical development, they allow the transition from isolation to the social relationship of the self. Progressively, the child must be directed towards playing sport, the pathway includes an initial phase that is connoted as spontaneous play, then, in a semi-structured and structured game, again, in a game-sport or mini-sport mode, and then arriving at the practice of real sport. In order to promote total well-being, it is essential to collaborate with other educational figures, such as parents, instructors, teachers and all those involved in the child's educational process. A complete, effective and global intervention can be achieved when each educational figure understands and embraces the educational and social mission, creating an educational network with other experts and operators. An effective educational network offers the subject educational continuity up to and including social integration and ultimately the realisation of a successful identity. Teaching methods for building contexts for motor and sports learning can increase opportunities for overall development and enhance the embedded dimension of the human, not only within the school discipline of physical education but also by integrating with other curricula through interdisciplinary teaching. The concept of interdisciplinary education recognises the integrity and uniqueness of each subject area, as well as the relationships between them. Interdisciplinarity together with the integrated curriculum (organised educational pathway) refer to an educational approach that aims at the overall development of the individual throughout his or her life.

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